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Analytic Hierarchy Process based Potential Risk Zonation of COVID-19 in India

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Abstract

COVID-19 caused by novel coronavirus (nCoV-19) declared by WHO as a pandemic has the potential to spread very fast thereby affecting a huge population. The first COVID-19 case in India was reported on 30th January, 2020, and in next three months, the number has soared to 33,050 despite a nationwide lockdown imposed on 25th March, 2020. Various states (provinces) of the country have been affected to varying extent. In this paper, an attempt has been made to delineate the potential risk zones of COVID-19 across entire country using Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Geographical Information System (GIS) on the basis of data released by government agencies. The resultant thematic map was classified into 6 risk zones viz. very high, high, moderate, slightly moderate, low and very low. Overall, one-third population of the country shall come under high risk zone followed by 26% in high risk zone, 10% in moderate risk zone, 29% in slightly moderate risk zone and 1% each in low and very low risk zones. Most populous/densely populated states are likely to be affected moderately or severely. The study reveals a pattern that the Central India shall witness a higher rate of COVID-19 cases whereas the Southern, extreme Northern and Northeastern states excluding Assam comparatively lower rate. The study found that three states, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh are likely to be very high risk zone owing to larger pressure of population over health facilities. Arunachal Pradesh, Goa, Mizoram, Sikkim and some other union territories are low risk zone whereas Himachal Pradesh and Andaman & Nicobar Islands fall under very low risk zone. Other states like Haryana, NCT of Delhi, Rajasthan and UT of Dadra & Nagar Haveli are likely to witness moderate risk of COVID-19 whereas Andhra Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir (undivided), Karnataka, Kerala, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Telangana, Tripura, Uttarakhand, West Bengal and UT of Lakshadweep will fall under slightly moderate risk zone.

Key - words: 1.COVID-19 pandemic, 2.Potential risk zonation, 3.Analytic Hierarchy Process, 4.India.

1. Introduction

The novel Coronavirus 2019 (nCoV-19) causing the human disease COVID-19 emerged first in Wuhan town of Hubei province of China in December 2019 [1]. The World Health Organization has declared COVID-19 as a pandemic which due to a very fast rate of human to human transmission has now spread to more than 180 countries within four month period infecting about 3.90 million people across the world with 0.218 million reported death [2]. nCoV-19 belongs to a large family of viruses causing less severe common cold to more severe diseases such as Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) and Middle East Respiratory Syndrome (MERS) [3]. It is very similar to the virus that caused SARS [4] however; its spread in human population has been remarkably faster than SARS and MERS that took respectively about 4 months and 2½ years to infect 1000 people [5].

India is the second most populated country in the world accounting for approximately 17% of the world population at present. Earlier during British-control, the country had also suffered heavily due to the pandemic of Spanish Influenza that prevailed from January 1918 to December 1919, and in three successive waves resulted into an estimated death toll of 13.88 million people [6]. Nevertheless, the Socio-economic conditions,

the health facilities and awareness have improved a lot in last 100 years in Independent India but still it is ranked as third world country with many of the human development indicators and health indices comparatively poor. Presently, 34,863 COVID-19 cases with 1154 death has been reported in the country as on 30th April, 2020 which has increased tremendously from 519 confirmed with 10 deaths as on 24th March 2019 (Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India). The increase in cases has been despite of the entire country been put under complete lockdown on 25th March 2020 by the government. As there is no vaccine yet available, avoidance of touching eyes, nose and mouth, hand washing with soap or use of alcohol-based hand sanitizers, face covering with proper quality mask, practicing respiratory hygiene and social distancing are the common measures to remain safe from viral infection [4]. Further, the regional disparities among various states of the country in terms of socio-economic conditions and health facilities may aggravate the situation in region specific manner.

Keeping in view, these disparities, an attempt has been made to prepare a thematic map delineating various states of the country into different risk zones using Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Geographical Information System (GIS) on the basis of the data obtained from various government agencies.

2. Methodology

15 multi-thematic layers were prepared separately on the basis of the promoting and controlling factors of Covid-19 (Table 1) using ArcGIS 10.3 software in similar geographic dimensions. The ancillary data was converted into raster format and reclassified for further processing. Multiple-criteria Decision Making (MCDM) technique i.e. Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) was used for assigning weights to each layer. Finally, weighted overlay analysis was carried out to generate the potential risk zones of COVID-19 in different states and Union territories of India.

2.1 Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)

AHP is a theory of measurement through pairwise comparisons and relies on the judgment of experts to derive priority scales. It is the scale that measures intangibles in relative terms. The comparisons are made using a scale of absolute judgment that represents how much one element dominates other with respect to given attributes [7]. The Saaty's 1 to 9 point scale values were assigned to each layer according to their influence on potential risk zones based on literature review and expert opinions. The weights thus assigned to thematic maps were normalized and the pair-wise comparison matrices of the assigned weights were prepared. The pairwise comparison matrix generated by MCDM (AHP) technique to evaluate the importance of two parameters or to find out the influence of a parameter over the other in risk evaluation has been shown in Table 2.

The relative importance was determined where value 1 denotes equal importance between the two parameters, and value 9 represents the extreme importance of one parameter compared to others. The normalized weight and consequently the relative weight of various thematic layers were generated on the basis of promoting and controlling factors respectively.

The normalized weights of the parameters were examined for consistency by computing consistency ratio (CR). The consistency ratio represents the probability that the matrix ratings were randomly generated. Then, the Consistency Index (CI) and Consistency Ratio (CR) were derived through the following equations:

$$CI = \frac{\lambda_{\max} - n}{n - 1} \quad (1)$$

Where, λ_{\max} represents the largest eigen value of the pair-wise comparison matrix, and 'n' denotes the number of parameters.

$$CR = \frac{CI}{\text{Random Consistency Index (RI)}} \quad (2)$$

Where, the value of RI (Table 3) was obtained from [7]. The value of CI should be always in between 0 to 0.1 for consistent weights. CR of 0.00 means the judgment of the pair-wise comparison matrix is perfectly consistent. If the CR exceeds 0.1, the corresponding weights should be re-evaluated to avoid inconsistency [7].

2.2 Overlay analysis

The parameters undertaken in the study are considered important in handling a pandemic situation. Integration of these factors with their potential weights was computed using weighted overlay analysis in GIS environment to delineate the potential risk zone (PRZ) as given below:

$$PRZ = (PN_wPN_r) + (PD_wPD_r) + (PU_wPU_r) + (EP_wEP_r) + (BP_wBP_r) + (CC_wCC_r) + (DC_wDC_r) + (TL_wTL_r) + (DD_wDD_r) + (HW_wHW_r) + (BD_wBD_r) + (PH_wPH_r) + (GH_wGH_r) + (GC_wGC_r) + (PC_wPC_r)$$

Where, PN: Population Distribution, PD: Population Density, PU: Percentage of Urban Population)EP: Elderly Population, BP: Population Below Poverty Line, CC: Confirmed COVID-19 Cases, DC: Death Cases due to COVID-19, TL: COVID-19 Testing Laboratories, DD: Density of Doctors, HW: Other Health Workers, BD: Beds available in public health facilities, PH: Public Health services, GH: Good Governance Health Index, GC: Good Governance Composite Index, and PC: Per Capita Income.

3. Results and discussion

The validity of the matrix was tested by consistency ratio that was 0.08, hence considered acceptable. Accordingly, all the thematic layers/parameters were assigned a suitable weight and all the sub-criteria were assigned relative ranks on the basis of their influence (Table 4a & 4b). Among the factors that seem to have a strong influence on expected prevalence of COVID-19 in India are (in sequential order): Number of confirmed Covid-19 cases (11.94%), Population below Poverty Line (8.40%), Percent urban population (8.09%), Projected population of the state (5.03%) and the Population density (4.44%). Elderly population and reported COVID-19 mortality at present are likely to have lesser influence (2.04% and 1.57% respectively) (Table 4a).

The factors that would control the prevalence of COVID-19 in India are likely to be (in sequential order): Number of COVID-19 Testing Laboratory (15.30%), Number of doctors (11.92%), Existing Public Health Facilities (8.95%), Good Governance Index- Public Health Ranking (5.83%), Number of other Health Workers (5.20%), Number of Hospital Beds in Public Health Service (4.32%) and Good Governance Index-Composite Ranking (4.05%). The Per Capita Income (2.92%) is expected to marginally influence the severity of the pandemic (Table 4b).

The thematic maps generated for each of the envisaged promoting and controlling factors of COVID-19 has been presented as Fig. 1(a-g) & Fig. 2(a-h) and the combined map of potential risk zone of COVID-19 generated thereof has been shown as Fig. 3. The map delineates the potential risk zones into Very high, High, Moderately high, Moderately low, Low and Very low categories.

The projected results on the basis of all the factors considered in this study reflects that Bihar, Madhya Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh would be in very high risk zones of COVID-19 and Assam, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Jharkhand, Maharashtra, Odisha and UT of Daman & Diu in high risk zone. Other states like Haryana, NCT of Delhi, Rajasthan and UT of Dadra & Nagar Haveli are likely to witness moderate risk of COVID-19 whereas Andhra Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir (undivided), Karnataka, Kerala, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Telangana, Tripura, Uttarakhand, West Bengal and UT of Lakshadweep will fall under slightly moderate risk zone. Comparatively lower prevalence of COVID-19 cases would be in Arunachal Pradesh, Goa, Mizoram, Sikkim and UTs of Chandigarh and Puducherry whereas very low infections are expected to be in Himachal Pradesh and UT of Andaman & Nicobar Islands. We found that three states namely, Bihar, Madhya Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh are likely to be under very high risk zone owing to larger pressure of population over health facilities.

Three most populated states scored poorly in terms of almost all disease controlling parameters, such as TL, PH, GH, HW, DD, BD and PC that are likely to play key role in favouring spread of the disease and resultant mortality. The governance composite score of these states is just moderate and comparatively lower than Kerala, Tamil Nadu and Himachal Pradesh which also have comparatively much higher governance health score. Though they have lesser number of reported COVID-19 cases at present, the total numbers of cases are likely to increase at much faster rate in these states. Overall these states represent one-third population of the country. Assam, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Jharkhand, Maharashtra Odisha and UT of Daman & Diu falls under high risk zone constituting 26% of the country's population. Further, 10% of the population covering the states of Haryana, NCT of Delhi, Rajasthan and UT of Dadra & Nagar Haveli are likely to witness moderate cases while 29% of population representing the states of Andhra Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir (undivided), Karnataka, Kerala, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Telangana, Tripura, Uttarakhand, West Bengal and UT of Lakshadweep may witness slightly moderate COVID-19 cases. A general pattern of higher rate of infections in the central parts of the country with comparatively lowering cases towards the extreme northern, southern and northeastern states excluding Assam emerges out of the study. It has been reported that the socio-economic development index of Southern states has been highly and symmetrically developed in comparison of Central and Northern states of India [8].

COVID-19 cases in larger states that have high population density shall be moderate to very high in number with high mortality as the public health facilities are inadequate. Further, it was also found in this study that a high percentage of BPL population that are present in many of the highly populated states that also have poor health facilities comes under high risk zones and vice-versa.

All hilly states of India shall fall between very low to slightly moderate risk zones. States and UTs where low (Arunachal Pradesh, Goa, Mizoram, Sikkim, Chandigarh and Puducherry) or very low (Himachal Pradesh and Andaman & Nicobar Islands) cases of infection shall be witnessed represent only 2% of the total population. These states have very low COVID-19 cases at present and most of them are distantly located from mainland India. They got more time to prepare themselves to fight the disease by imposing strict restrictions on movement of the people from other states. These were also the reasons for low occurrence of the Spanish Influenza in remote regions of the country that were distantly located from Bombay, the entry point of the disease [9].

Adequate number of COVID-19 testing laboratories and the number of specimens being tested is most crucial for timely identification of positive cases and their immediate quarantine so as to prevent further spread of the disease in a community [10]. The data shows that Bihar, Madhya Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh have the least numbers of testing laboratories and therefore likely to be highly vulnerable states. It has been well recognized that laboratory diagnostic capacity can effectively contain outbreak of disease¹¹. Therefore, unless the country increases its COVID-19 testing capacity with high reliability both at state and national level, the containment of disease outbreak will be a challenging task.

Research on health inequalities has systematically highlighted the large disparities across health outcomes that exist in India [12, 13]. Hence, effective management of hospital facilities, deployment of doctors, other health workers and ancillary support teams for rapid contact tracing of all identified positive cases may play vital role in slowing down the spread of COVID-19 [14].

4. Conclusions

The study unveils the applicability of geospatial techniques in delineating potential risk zones of COVID-19 in the coming days. The number of confirmed cases, Population below Poverty Line and Percent urban population appears to play influential role on the expected prevalence of Covid-19 while number of Testing Laboratory, number of doctors and existing Public Health Facilities are likely to control the prevalence to a greater extent. The delineated potential risk zone map shows three most populated states of the country namely Bihar, Madhya Pradesh and Uttar Pradesh under Very high risk zone owing to larger

pressure of population over health facilities. Assam, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Jharkhand, Maharashtra Odisha and UT of Daman & Diu figure under High risk zone. On the other hand, Arunachal Pradesh, Goa, Mizoram, Sikkim and UTs of Chandigarh and Puducherry will have comparatively lower prevalence whereas Himachal Pradesh and Andaman & Nicobar Islands would have very low infections of COVID-19. The findings show a probability of higher rate of infections in the central parts of the country with comparatively lowering cases towards the extreme northern, southern and northeastern states excluding Assam. Adequate COVID-19 testing capacity in all states for timely identification of positive cases for their immediate quarantine may slow down spread of the disease.

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Table 1: Database and sources used in the study

Sl. No.	Factors	Sources	Remark
1.	State-wise projected population, 2020	National Health Profile, 2019, Central Bureau of Health Intelligence, Govt. of India	-
2.	State-wise projected population density, 2020	National Health Profile, 2019, and Census of India, 2011, Govt. of India	Projected population/area
3.	Percentage of urban population (2020)	Population Projections for India and States 2011-2036, National Commission on Population Ministry of Health & Family Welfare.	
4.	Elderly population	Population Census 2011, after Elderly in India, 2016, Central Statistics Office, Govt. of India	-
5.	Population below poverty line	NITI Aayog, after Progress Report, 2020, Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Govt. of India	-
6.	Confirmed COVID-19 cases (As on 30 th April, 08:00 GMT +5:30)	www.mygov.in , Govt. of India	-
7.	Death COVID-19 cases (As on 30 th April, 08:00 GMT +5:30)	www.mygov.in , Govt. of India	-
8.	Number of Testing Laboratories for COVID-19 (as on 29/04/2020)	Indian Council of Medical Research, Department of Health Research, Govt. of India	Govt. and Pvt. operational testing laboratories
9.	Density of Doctors	The Health Workforce in India,	Human Resources for

		World Health Organization.	Health Observer Series No. 16
10.	Density of other Health Workers	The Health Workforce in India, World Health Organization.	Human Resources for Health Observer Series No. 16
11.	Beds available in public health facilities	Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt. of India	-
12.	Public health facilities	Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Govt. of India	PHC, CHC, SDH and DH
13.	Good Governance Index (Public Health Ranking)	Department of Administrative Reforms & Public Grievances, Govt. of India	-
14.	Good Governance Index (Composite Ranking)	Department of Administrative Reforms & Public Grievances, Govt. of India	-
15.	Per Capita Income of states	Economic & Statistical Organisation, Punjab and Central Statistical Organisation, New Delhi after www.esopb.gov.in	-

PHC – Primary Health Centre, CHC – Community Health Centre, SHC – Sub-District/Divisional Health Centre, DH – District Hospital.

Table 2: Pairwise comparison matrix and normalized weight

	PN	PD	PU	EP	BP	CC	DC	TL	DD	HW	BD	PH	GH	GC	PC	Criteria Weight
PN	1.00	2.00	0.25	4.00	0.25	0.20	3.00	0.33	0.25	3.00	2.00	0.50	0.33	0.50	4.00	0.0503
PD	0.50	1.00	0.33	3.00	0.25	0.33	4.00	0.25	0.25	2.00	3.00	0.50	0.33	1.00	2.00	0.0444
PU	4.00	3.00	1.00	5.00	1.00	0.50	4.00	0.50	0.50	2.00	0.50	0.50	2.00	3.00	4.00	0.0809
EP	0.25	0.33	0.20	1.00	0.25	0.25	3.00	0.20	0.25	0.50	0.33	0.25	0.25	0.33	0.33	0.0204
BP	4.00	4.00	1.00	4.00	1.00	0.50	4.00	0.50	0.50	2.00	3.00	0.33	2.00	2.00	4.00	0.0840
CC	5.00	3.00	2.00	4.00	2.00	1.00	5.00	0.50	1.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	0.1194
DC	0.33	0.25	0.25	0.33	0.25	0.20	1.00	0.20	0.20	0.25	0.33	0.20	0.33	0.33	0.25	0.0157
TL	3.00	4.00	2.00	5.00	2.00	2.00	5.00	1.00	2.00	3.00	4.00	4.00	3.00	4.00	3.00	0.1530
DD	4.00	4.00	2.00	4.00	2.00	1.00	5.00	0.50	1.00	3.00	3.00	2.00	3.00	3.00	4.00	0.1192
HW	0.33	0.50	0.50	2.00	0.50	0.33	4.00	0.33	0.33	1.00	3.00	0.50	2.00	2.00	3.00	0.0520
BD	0.50	0.33	2.00	3.00	0.33	0.33	3.00	0.25	0.33	0.33	1.00	0.25	0.50	2.00	2.00	0.0432
PH	2.00	2.00	2.00	4.00	3.00	0.33	5.00	0.25	0.50	2.00	4.00	1.00	2.00	2.00	3.00	0.0895
GH	3.00	3.00	0.50	4.00	0.50	0.33	3.00	0.33	0.33	0.50	2.00	0.50	1.00	2.00	3.00	0.0583
GC	2.00	1.00	0.33	3.00	0.50	0.50	3.00	0.25	0.33	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	1.00	2.00	0.0405
PC	0.25	0.50	0.25	3.00	0.25	0.33	4.00	0.33	0.25	0.33	0.50	0.33	0.33	0.50	1.00	0.0292

PN: Population Distribution, PD: Population Density, PU: Percentage of Urban Population, EP: Elderly Population, BP: Population Below Poverty Line, CC: Confirmed COVID-19 Cases, DC: Death Cases due to COVID-19, TL: COVID-19 Testing Laboratories, DD: Density of Doctors, HW: Other Health Workers, BD: Beds

available in public health facilities, PH: Public Health services, GH: Good Governance Health Index, GC: Good Governance Composite Index, and PC: Per Capita Income.

Table 3: Random consistency indices (RI) for different criteria (Saaty, 1980).

N	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
RI	0	0	0.58	0.9	1.12	1.24	1.32	1.41	1.45	1.49	1.51	1.53	1.56	1.57	1.59

Table 4a: Relative weight of COVID-19 promoting factors

Sl. No.	Theme	Classes	Intensity	Ranks	Normalized Weights	Influence (%)
1.	Projected Population ('000)	Upto 10000	Very Low	1	0.0503	5.03
		10001 - 40000	Low	2		
		40001 - 80000	Moderately Low	3		
		80001 - 120000	Moderate	4		
		120001 - 160000	Moderately High	5		
		160001 - 200000	High	6		
		Above 200000	Very High	7		
2.	Projected Population Density, 2020 (per km ²)	Upto 150	Very Low	1	0.0444	4.44
		151 - 300	Low	2		
		301 - 600	Moderately Low	3		
		601 - 900	Moderate	4		
		901 - 1200	Moderately High	5		
		1201 - 3000	High	6		
		Above 3000	Very High	7		
3.	Projected Urban Population (%)	Upto 15	Very Low	1	0.0809	8.09
		15 - 30	Low	2		
		30 - 45	Moderately Low	3		
		45 - 60	Moderate	4		
		60 - 75	Moderately High	5		
		75 - 90	High	6		
		Above 90	Very High	7		
4.	Elderly Population (%)	Upto 2	Very Low	1	0.0204	2.04
		2 - 4	Low	2		
		4 - 6	Moderately Low	3		
		6 - 8	Moderate	4		
		8 - 10	Moderately High	5		
		10 - 12	High	6		
		Above 12	Very High	7		
5.	Population Below Poverty Line (%)	Upto 5	Good	1	0.0840	8.40
		5 - 10	Approaching to Good	2		
		10 - 15	Fair	3		

		15 - 20	Approaching to Fair	4		
		20 - 25	Poor	5		
		25 - 30	Approaching to Poor	6		
		Above 30	Bad	7		
6.	Confirmed cases of Covid-19 (per million population)	Upto 25	Very Low	1	0.1194	11.94
		26 - 50	Low	2		
		51 - 75	Moderately Low	3		
		76 - 100	Moderate	4		
		101 - 125	Moderately High	5		
		126 - 150	High	6		
		Above 150	Very High	7		
7.	Percentage of Death cases Out of the total confirmed cases of COVID-19	No Death	Good	1	0.0157	1.57
		Upto 2	Approaching to Fair	2		
		2 - 4	Fair	3		
		4 - 6	Approaching to Poor	4		
		6 - 8	Poor	5		
		8 - 10	Approaching to Bad	6		
		Above 10	Bad	7		

Table 4b: Relative weight of COVID-19 controlling factors

Sl. No.	Theme	Classes	Intensity	Ranks	Normalized Weights	Influence (%)
1.	Number of Testing laboratories (per million population)	Upto 0.5	Very Low	7	0.1530	15.30
		0.5 - 1.0	Low	6		
		1.0 - 1.5	Moderately Low	5		
		1.5 - 2.0	Moderate	4		
		2.0 - 2.5	Moderately High	3		
		2.5 - 3.0	High	2		
		Above 3.0	Very High	1		
2.	Density of Doctors (per million population)	Upto 2.9	Very Low	7	0.1192	11.92
		3.0 - 4.9	Low	6		
		5.0 - 7.9	Moderately Low	5		
		8.0 - 11.9	Moderate	4		
		12.0 - 15.9	Moderately High	3		
		16.0 - 19.9	High	2		
		Above 19.9	Very High	1		
3.	Density of other Health Workers (per million population)	Upto 10	Very Low	7	0.0520	5.20
		10 - 20	Low	6		
		20 - 30	Moderately Low	5		
		30 - 40	Moderate	4		

		40 - 50	Moderately High	3		
		50 - 60	High	2		
		Above 60	Very High	1		
4.	Number of Beds available in public health facilities (per million population)	Upto 2.5	Very Low	7	0.0432	4.32
		2.5 - 5.0	Low	6		
		5.0 - 7.5	Moderately Low	5		
		7.5 - 10.0	Moderate	4		
		10.0 - 12.5	Moderately High	3		
		12.5 - 15.0	High	2		
		Above 15.0	Very High	1		
		5.	Number of Public Health Facilities (per million population)	Upto 0.2		
0.2 - 0.4	Low			6		
0.4 - 0.6	Moderately Low			5		
0.6 - 0.8	Moderate			4		
0.8 - 1.0	Moderately High			3		
1.0 - 1.2	High			2		
Above 1.2	Very High			1		
6.	Good Governance Index (Public Health Ranking)	Upto 0.20	Bad	7	0.0583	5.83
		0.20 - 0.30	Approaching to poor	6		
		0.30 - 0.40	Poor	5		
		0.40 - 0.50	Approaching to Fair	4		
		0.50 - 0.65	Fair	3		
		0.65 - 0.80	Approaching to Good	2		
		Above 0.80	Good	1		
7.	Good Governance Index (Composite Ranking)	Upto 3.0	Bad	7	0.0405	4.05
		3.0 - 3.5	Approaching to poor	6		
		3.5 - 4.0	Poor	5		
		4.0 - 4.5	Approaching to Fair	4		
		4.5 - 5.0	Fair	3		
		5.0 - 5.5	Approaching to Good	2		
		Above 5.5	Good	1		
8.	Per Capita Income (Rs.)	Upto 50000	Very Low	7	0.0292	2.92
		50000 - 100000	Low	6		
		100000 - 150000	Moderately Low	5		
		150000 - 200000	Moderate	4		
		200000 - 250000	Moderately High	3		
		250000 -	High	2		

		300000			
		Above 300000	Very High	1	

Fig. 1: Thematic maps of promoting factors: A- Projected population distribution ('000); B- Population density (km²); C- Projected urban population (%); D- Elderly Population of 60 years and above (%); E- BPL population (%); F- Confirmed COVID-19 cases (per million of population); G- Percentage of population death due to COVID-19

Fig. 2: Thematic maps of controlling factor: A- No. of testing laboratory (per million of population); B- Density of doctor (per million of population); C- No. of other health workers (per million of population); D- No. of bed available in public health facilities (per million of population); E- No. of public health facilities (per million of population); F- Good governance index (public health ranking); G- Good governance index (composite ranking); H- Per capita income (Rupees).

Fig. 3: Potential Risk Zones of COVID-19 in India

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